

1 Concept note for D4.7 EU & MS Route-maps

18th January 2024, Kirsty Blackstock

This concept note is v2.0 that builds on the initial concept note from September 2022 ([here](#)) and relates to T4.6.

The focus is on the **European level routemap** due to **M4.6** (Draft combined route-map for EC (**Due Month 36**) (JHI) - Draft route-map available). Ideas for MS routemaps are provided in that section.

The final products will be:

- A European (EU) routemap (due July 25)
- N (TBC) Member State routemaps (each a standalone document that will also be annexes in the EU routemap) (due July 25)
- An EU infographic (not in DoA but discussed and agreed with Astrid)

The formal request in the DoA is D4.7 EU and Member State route-maps for mainstreaming restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems across sectors using policy and commercial governance levers to inform review of EU 2030 Strategy and Green Deal implementation (**Month 46**) – WWF HU with a M4.8 due month 48.

1.1 Differences to 1st Concept Note

Main differences from the original concept note are listed below:

[add here – separate guidance on D4.5, changes to D4.8, drop focus groups, maybe less than 7 MS routemaps]

1.2 Guiding Principles

The routemap(s) should reflect these principles:

1. They build on and synthesize what we have learnt from WP4 and wider MERLIN project
2. They are written for, and in dialogue with, their audience
3. They complement the existing guidance on mainstreaming/scaling up restoration and NbS
4. They have a niche that is otherwise missing
5. Concise, visually appealing, practical

1.3 Purpose and Function of a routemap

A routemap (or roadmap) provides a strategic framework for suggested actions (REF)

Used by EC and National initiatives (examples)

Not prescriptive recommendations, suggestions of how to achieve your goal, including who does what, how conditions might affect choices etc. Not as formal or structured as an action plan, as it provides options and ability to differentiate between short, medium and long-term options; or low-cost or high-cost opportunities. Suggestions of how you might get to a final destination; with options of how to get there, how long it might take etc.

It works with the metaphor of planning a journey. Requires – a final **destination & starting point**; and information about how to get from one to the other. There may be constraints or preferences for which route is taken.

To get from start to destination – we need

- (1) awareness that a change is needed;
- (2) awareness that actors can be and should be part of the change;
- (3) identify things to change (personal, political, practical)
- (4) Identify changes the actors can develop (CREATE); changes they can MAINTAIN and things that need to be disrupted to allow creation and maintenance to occur
- (5) Identify changes that other actors can develop (CREATE); changes they can MAINTAIN and things that need to be disrupted to allow sectoral creation and maintenance to occur
 - a. Particular focus on policy, value chains and just transitions as potential approaches to what to change and how/why/where to do it for steps 4 & 5
- (6) How these options and ideas can co-exist and work together avoiding conflicts and unintended consequences

It should be SMART (**specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound**).

The objective of the routemap(s) is to provide a clear, publicly accessible written record of what has been learnt about transformation in how the sectors support mainstreaming freshwater NbS, that the relevant stakeholders/actors support and intend to use in the future.

1.4 Focus

1.4.1 Overall focus

MERLIN is focussed on meeting GD goals by freshwater NbS/restoration – to get this to happen everywhere we need an intersection of multiple sectors, policies and stakeholders working together.

This means collective working across sectors and policy domains but also dealing with trade-offs and conflicts.

The overall goal of MERLIN WP4 is.... a co-constructed plan* to mainstream NbS building on existing levers, identifying new levers and disrupting levers working against FW NbS

Focus here, on the need to involve the sectors, and to do this cross-sectorally. Not just for public sector (and NGOs) to do – societal benefits needs a whole of society approach. Summary of literature on the need for private sector to take responsibility, get benefits from NbS.

We could include ideas about greenwashing and greenwishing here?

starting point (problem statement, also opportunity statement) – information on the state of the environment, cost of environmental damage/GHG to the economy, rationale for the Green Deal, change is needed, something positive about gains from helping nature.

This is relatively clear but need to focus on statements of need for cross-sectoral working, opportunities from cross-sectoral working, threats/problems if we don't have cross-sectoral working

Destination: all relevant actors implementing the plan* in order to achieve the Green Deal?

see (MIRO) where we started on this vision/destination. Also more here on the benefits of achieving the Green Deal and NRL/WFD etc?

Shall we test this starting point and destination definitions at APM?

1.4.2 Main cross-sectoral issues

To date, the cross sectoral opportunities seem to be:

- Shared problems e.g. too much or too little water affects agriculture, navigation, Natcat insurance, Water supply - are the solutions in the Sectoral Strategies dependent on actions by other sectors (check this)
- Need to respond to societal pressure to reduce environmental harm e.g. agriculture, hydropower, peat extraction are the solutions in the Sectoral Strategies dependent on actions by other sectors (check this)
- Shared interventions e.g. shared impoundments (agri, hydro, WSS) or dykes (navi, agri, insurance?) – do we have examples of working together to remove dykes/reconnect side arms, impoundments by more than one sector (CS7a?)
- Need to implement in catchment with upstream/downstream interactions involving different land/water users
- Enabling role of other sectors (bio-economy, tourism) to make NbS more viable, acceptable
- Role of VCs – do they sometimes encourage interaction between sectors as well as within sectors?

[Fanni noted that she was starting an excel database to collect these examples?]

The cross-sectoral problems seem to be:

- Lack of joined up policies and plans
- Lack of forums getting input from different sectors about how they are affected or could contribute to implementation of freshwater NbS e.g. in strategic planning processes
- Lack of resources (public funding, private finance, human capacity) or funding tied to sectoral specific outcome, not wider improvement of the catchment?
- Sense that there are not win-win but win-lose involved in NbS (suspicion, mistrust) – and lack of mechanisms for sharing costs or benefits? (Justice)
- Different goals or visions for ‘success’
- Lack of monitoring or showing benefits for multiple sectors/perspectives
- Lack of data on multiple benefits (see indicators and Theory of Change work in WP1)

[Kirsty has been collecting reports and papers about this but not yet read anything, sorry]

Need to make a decision about how much we focus on what we’ve learnt from MERLIN (see section 1.7) and how much we draw in other examples and evidence.

Although this is about collective action and coordination in specific places, it will not be a ‘spatial’ analysis using primarily GIS based data (a common problem – two very different understandings of spatial planning).

Cross sectoral doesn’t mean blame shifting! Means collective responsibility and sharing of roles.

Kirsty to scan yellow post it notes from Fulda again....

1.4.3 Link to Sectoral Strategies and Value chain analysis

Complementary to sectoral strategies that focus on the specific actions by individual sectors

Complementary to value chain analyses that focus on specific opportunities for individual sectors

Builds on and pulls material together (across the sectors, combining sectoral insights, VC, Justice/stakeholder insights and policy insights)

[do we include financing here from WP3F?]

See section 1.7

1.5 Audience – who is planning their journey?

Informing those designing and reviewing coherent policies (EU institutions); and those implementing policies in a more coherent way – particularly the combination of CSPs, NECPs, RBMPs/FRMPs, Adaptation Strategies and proposed NRPlans

Sectoral strategies are for sectors and those doing NbS with/for sectors

Routemaps are for those actors and organisations who bring sectors together.

Mainly public sector/NGOs

those from sectors who want to work in partnership projects

those enable this cross-sectoral working (e.g. advisors, consultants, financiers)

EU and MS are for European and National level stakeholders. We assume RSP are for the local level/regional level actors involved in the specific CS.

This is targeted at professional and organised stakeholder groups, it ignores the role of individual consumers, business operators, residents, volunteers, visitors etc. These are important but would need different research.

Think about when and how to interact with these stakeholders for input/feedback on the focus and choice of options to work up the details (see 1.11.5)

1.6 Niche – complementary to existing guidance

We start from these propositions:

- There is a lot of guidance on upscaling, mainstreaming, transition and transformations

Definitions of these terms needed

- Build on what is available, there is guidance on NbS and freshwaters but tends to be urban and case study based
- Therefore, there is a need for guidance that relates to large-scale, rural, interventions
- Targeted to audiences above

1.6.1 List here the existing guidance to complement

1.7 Inputs from MERLIN

Some new reviews, data collection and analysis but also building on recommendations from D4.1, 4.3 (now) and D4.2, D4.4, D4.5 to come during 2024.

[D4.8/T4.7??? – I assume we are not planning to do more here except where it already provides guidance in section 1.6.1]

Also insights from Green Deal indicators, RSPs, modelling (these are being summarised in the CS notes but need to be updated all the time)

Insights on stakeholder engagement from WP1-5 already covered by T4.2

1.8 Workplan and milestones

See slides here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1vLPWRxH76HZZyYZiBzWE8SE7zkKyLvih?usp=drive_link

- Agree outline (due now)
- Dissemination processes and NRL updates (Jan/Feb)
- Methodology by APM; decision on which MS routemaps (Anna suggested before Vienna, maybe afterwards now?)
- Drafting from April
- Draft ready by September for cross-sectoral workshop(s)

1.8.1 Actions for us to do to start drafting

TBD

1.9 Thoughts on MS plans

The rationale for MS routemaps is to show different routes or paths to transformation; depending on the geographical, socio-economic and political context.

Routemap is for the six MERLIN economic sectors in Europe but will need to reflect on the different legal/administrative contexts in member states¹ for sectors and also understand different experiences in individual sites/regions² – so some illustrations of different routes according to these different places.

[We are not planning to divide up the routemap by geography e.g. E, W, N, S Europe or by the case clusters - difference to WP3 upscaling plan – about the institutional changes that these sectors might make and how these institutions interact, not about where to intervene]

Depends on partner interest and support?

Also some RSPs are almost MS routemaps already – work with them, or do others that don't have this already?

1.10 Thoughts on connections to D3.6 European Scalability Plan

D4.7 is not spatial but focussed on institutional processes – ESP will be driven by where upscaling can take place and then how to make it happen.

How to make it happen can duplicate with our sectoral strategies and routemaps.

We are not planning to divide up the routemap by geography e.g. E, W, N, S Europe or by the case clusters - difference to WP3 upscaling plan – about the institutional changes that these sectors might make and how these institutions interact, not about where to intervene

Discussion of these links is proposed for the APM in Vienna (Thursday afternoon) although not currently on the agenda circulated by Sebastian.

Not clear if/how RSPs and ESP will be linked together.

Kirsty presented some ideas on this at SG meeting June 23 see slides here: <https://nx19846.your-storage.de/f/604726>

¹ We will choose from: Basque/Spain; Netherlands; Austria, Romania, Hungary, Portugal, Finland, UK (TBC Germany, Denmark, and Belgium also interesting?)

² We anticipate a focus on: CS 2 (Basque) 4 (Rhine) 7 (Danube-upstream) 8 (Danube – downstream) 9 (Tisza), 13 (Sorraia) and 17 (Forth). TBC after Fulda meeting and review of optimisation strategies... we probably should add CS 14 (Finnish peat extraction).

1.11 Outline for the Deliverable

Kirsty to check outline for RSP and see if that is good model

1.11.1 Intro (what is a routemap, who for, what our definition of the sectors)

Drawing on sections 1.3, 1.4, 1.5 and 1.6

Definition of the sectors from the sectoral strategies

1.11.2 Context

– what is the starting point and why need to move/go to another destination (push factors) – see the overview of the problem in D4.1, D4.3 and D4.4/4.2/4.5

1.11.3 What is the destination?

restoration using NbS that helps their business/sector – (pull factors) – see vision/goal in section 1.4

Definitions of NbS, transformations etc here

1.11.4 What are the options for the journey?

Taking the six sector strategies – identify areas of conflict or synergy and then focus on options to overcome conflict or increase synergy in some main cases

This has been started in section 1.4.2 above

From a short list of main areas of conflict to address or synergies to amplify, identify some options

See also section 1.4.2 above

1.11.5 For each option:

- What it is,
- how it could be done,
- who (else) is needed to do it,
- how/if it requires interaction with other sectors.
- when,
- where (all EU or just some places) and
- one or more examples with pictures &
- where to get more information

1.11.6 Summary

1.11.7 References